

Assessment of the corrosion resistance of self-ordered anodic aluminum oxide (AAO) obtained in tartaric-sulfuric acid (TSA)

Leandro González-Rovira^{a*}, Lorena González-Souto^a, Pedro Astola^b, Cristina Bravo-Benítez^b, Francisco Javier Botana^a.

^a Departamento de Ciencia de los Materiales e Ingeniería Metalúrgica y Química Inorgánica, Universidad de Cádiz, Escuela Superior de Ingeniería, Puerto Real (Cádiz), 11519, Spain

^b Titania, Ensayos y Proyectos Industriales S.L. Ed. RETSE, nave 4, 11500, El Puerto de Santa María. Spain.

* Corresponding author: leandro.gonzalez@uca.es

Abstract

The corrosion performance of self-ordered porous anodic aluminum oxide (AAO) has been studied and correlated to its structure. High purity aluminum alloy (>99.999%) has been anodized using three different conditions: (a) in tartaric-sulfuric electrolyte employing common disordered conditions (TSA), (b) in sulfuric acid applying self-ordering conditions (SA), and (c) in tartaric-sulfuric electrolyte applying self-ordering conditions (TSA-SA). Some samples were post-treated in boiling water with the aim of sealing their pores. The morphology and order of the AAOs were determined by means of scanning electron microscopy and Fast Fourier Transform (FFT), while their corrosion behavior was assessed in 0.59 M NaCl employing potentiodynamic polarization tests (LP) and electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS). The evolution of impedance of samples SA and TSA was monitored during 1000 hours of

immersion in 0.59 M NaCl. The three types of samples present similar pore diameter (D_{po}) and certain degree of order, although TSA shows the lowest. However, TSA shows smaller interpore distance (D_{int}), thinner cell wall thickness (t_w) and higher pore density (ρ_{po}) and porosity (P) than SA and TSA-SA, which feature very similar values for these structural parameters. The LP curves do not allow to discriminate between samples. SA and TSA-SA have higher impedance than TSA among samples not sealed, probably because a thicker barrier layer forms in samples with self-ordering regime. When sealed, TSA samples show higher impedance than SA and TSA-SA in the medium frequency range because porous membranes with lower order are more easily sealed. All types of AAO, both unsealed and sealed, undergo self-sealing process during the immersion experiments. According to EIS interpretation, TSA porous oxide is self-sealed in a more efficient manner than SA and TSA-SA. These findings imply that self-ordering conditions can enhance the corrosion resistance of AAO.

Keywords: Aluminum, Anodic aluminum oxide, Two-step anodizing, Tartaric-sulfuric anodizing, Corrosion, EIS.

1. Introduction

Anodizing is known since 1920 and can be applied on aluminum alloys and other passivable alloys, such as those of titanium, magnesium, zinc, niobium, and tantalum [1-7]. It is possible to find in the literature a large number of substances that have been proposed as electrolytes in anodizing baths [1, 8-11]. However, the applications at industrial scale are mainly limited to the use of sulfuric, phosphoric, oxalic, and chromic acids.

The chromic acid anodizing (CAA) has been used for decades in the aluminum industry in general and in the aerospace field in particular, thanks to not only good anticorrosive properties of the anodic layers obtained but also to be a very robust process. However, the chrome has the disadvantage of being toxic and polluting, especially the Cr (VI). As a result, approximately from the last decade of the 20th century, there has been an important research activity related to the search for more ecological alternatives to processes based on the use of chromium [12-15].

The main alternatives to CAA that have been developed are based on solutions of other acids or mixtures of them. Thus, the aero-industry has implemented the boric-sulfuric acid (BSAA) [16-18] and the tartaric-sulfuric acid anodizing (TSA) [19-22]. Other processes studied are the thin film sulfuric acid anodizing (SAA), developed by Lockheed Martin Aeronautics [23,24] and the plasma electrolytic oxidation (PEO), also known as microarc oxidation. The latter is similar to anodizing, but it employs much higher voltages, so that electric sparks are produced and the resulting plasma provides special features to the structure of the generated oxide [25-26].

In the case of the European aeronautical industry, the TSA has been implemented as an alternative to CAA from January 2014. However, although TSA reduces environmental impact and health risks, shows some disadvantages when compared to CAA. Firstly, the tartaric acid is more expensive. Secondly, the reduced robustness of the process, that suffers from being

more prone to fungi development and more sensitive to contaminants. And finally, a lower corrosion resistance. CAA sealed with chromates could last even more than 1000 hours in salt spray chamber test meeting the requirement of number of pits per area [16.]. Meanwhile, TSA sealed with Cr-free solutions stand less than 500 hours [20, 27, 28], which makes them difficult to apply where there are special harsh working conditions such as in helicopters or military aircrafts. Thus, the TSA has still a margin of improvement and companies and academia are investing important amount of resources to develop new alternatives. The research lines in this topic can be grouped in two approaches. The first one focuses on the anodizing itself, studying how to modify the electrolyte or the mechanism involved in the growing of the alumina layer as a via to optimize the experimental variables [11, 19, 29-33]. The second approach is the development of new sealing post-treatment to overcome the results of Cr-free technologies [20, 27, 28, 34-38].

The work here reported aims to increase the corrosion performance of TSA and is in line with the first research line, exploring the modification of the anodizing although with a disruptive perspective. The methodology here chosen to modify the process of anodizing has its origin in a particular type of self-ordering anodizing so-called two steps anodizing. These treatments are known since the 1990s [39] and using certain experimental conditions allow to obtain anodic porous alumina films showing long range order. This kind of anodic alumina layers are those referred as *ordered* layers. The methodology of two-step anodizing is schematized in Fig. 1. The first anodization is applied during several hours and produces a porous AAO with not completely ordered structure. This first anodic layer is therefore removed, typically in a mixture of phosphoric acid and chromic acid, resulting a surface textured with arrays of almost hemispherical holes. Then, the second anodization is carried out with the textured aluminum under the same conditions employed for the first anodization. In these conditions, the ordered porous layers are obtained. The pores of this second AAO are formed at the centers of each concave hole and grow normal to the aluminum surface. Each cylindrical pore and its

surrounding oxide area constitute a hexagonal cell which are organized in a hexagonal close-packed arrangement, forming a honeycomb-like structure. Other important characteristics of two-step anodizing are the employment of low temperatures of the electrolyte, usually in the order of a 0-5 °C, and the possibility to obtain layers of even hundreds of microns of thickness [40, 41]. These treatments contrast with TSA industrial anodizing, that requires only one anodization during less than 30 minutes, temperatures above room temperature and give rise to disordered porous anodic layers with 2-7 microns of thickness [42]. To date, ordered porous anodic layers have been applied to numerous fields as such as separation [43], chemical/biological sensing devices [44], cell adhesion [45], catalysis [46], energy storage [47] and drug delivery vehicles [48], being the most remarkable the employment as a template for the synthesis of nanostructures inside their pores [40,49].

However, studies of the implementation and the performance of ordered AAO layers as protection against corrosion are scarce and shallow. Bouchama *et al* [50] compared the corrosion performance of anodic films formed by one-step and two-step anodization performed on pure aluminum in 1M H₂SO₄ at 5 °C and applying 25 V. EIS measurements in NaCl and SEM images indicated that the morphology and the corrosion resistance of anodic film formed by two-step anodizing process are very improved if compared to single one. EIS data for layers immersed in 3% NaCl solution for 30 hours show lower resistance of the porous layer (R_p) and barrier layer (R_b) for single-step anodizing process, starting from 30 kΩcm² both of them and going down to 5 kΩcm² and near 0 kΩcm², respectively. Conversely, a gradual increase in R_p and R_b until the end of immersion time is observed for two-step anodizing process. They start at 10 kΩcm² and 20 kΩcm², respectively, and reached values close to 70 kΩcm² in both cases. Lee and Kim [51] applied two-step anodizing on naval 5083 aluminum alloy in H₂SO₄ with concentrations ranging from 5-20 vol.% at 10 °C in the galvanostatic regime of 20 mA/cm². The anodized samples showed, as expected, lower corrosion current density than the bare metal when studied by potentiodynamic polarization measurements. Non-anodized samples featured

$2.09 \cdot 10^{-7} \text{ A/cm}^2$, while samples anodized at 5 vol%, 10 vol%, 15 vol% and 20 vol% obtained $6.16 \cdot 10^{-8} \text{ A/cm}^2$, $2.29 \cdot 10^{-8} \text{ A/cm}^2$, $2.94 \cdot 10^{-9} \text{ A/cm}^2$ and $1.53 \cdot 10^{-9} \text{ A/cm}^2$, respectively. However, they do not compare against conventional anodization. Mehdizade *et al* [52] studied ordered and pulsed anodizing of pure aluminum in oxalic acid electrolyte, although the temperature, 17 °C, sounds to be a bit higher for self-ordering regime. They applied three different pulses: positive pulse voltage (PPV) at 50 V and 0 V, pulse reverse voltage (PRV) at 50 V and -7 V, and direct pulse voltage (DPV) at 48 V and 29 V. DPV pulsed mode led to the lower porosity and better corrosion behavior according to potentiodynamic polarization tests and EIS. Thus, DPV showed density of corrosion current of $0.195 \mu\text{A/cm}^2$, $0.229 \mu\text{A/cm}^2$, $0.693 \mu\text{A/cm}^2$ and $1.967 \mu\text{A/cm}^2$ for samples anodized during 60 minutes, 90 minutes, 120 minutes and 150 minutes, respectively. Meanwhile, the resistance of the barrier layer (Rb) of the sample DPV anodized during 90 minutes was $7041 \Omega\text{cm}^2$. The explanation argued was a moderate increase in the temperature in the electrolyte in comparison with PPV and PRV modes.

In this context, this article aims at the assessment of the corrosion behavior of alumina coatings obtained with two-step anodizing, and compare this corrosion behavior against TSA anodizing. In particular, we work with the hypothesis that it is possible to enhance the resistance to corrosion of porous anodic alumina by increasing the order of the porous structure and by controlling the dimension of its characteristic elements down to the nanoscale: thickness of the barrier layer and pore diameter. This hypothesis considers the behavior of coatings both unsealed and sealed, so that it is expected to improve the results of the sealing step.

The work here presented was obtained in the framework of a project which explored the application of nanotechnology to improve the TSA anodization performed in the aerospace industry. The behaviour against corrosion of anodic layers obtained by means of two-step anodizing was assessed during the initial phases of the project at laboratory scale, and contrasted against TSA. Afterwards, the project focused on the adaptation of the two-step

anodizing to an industrial scenario employing a pilot plant and different experimental conditions, such as shorter processing times and various commercial aluminium alloys.

2. Experimental

2.1. Preparation of oxide layers

The starting anodizing material was a high purity aluminum alloy (>99.999%) in the form of discs (25 mm diameter, 0.25 mm thick) and supplied by Goodfellow. Before anodizing, the aluminum samples were pre-treated using two consecutive surface treatments: degreasing with acetone and electropolishing in a HClO₄/EtOH (vol/vol = 1:3) solution at 0 °C applying 20 V during 4 minutes using a Grelco GDL3040 power supply. Anodizing was performed exposing 1.5 cm² of one face of the samples to an electrochemical cells of 125 mL of capacity, and under constant voltage conditions. Table 1 summarizes the experimental details employed in each anodization treatment to obtain 3 types of samples, labelled as TSA, SA and TSA-SA. TSA samples were fabricated using the same electrolyte, temperature and voltage cycle as in the industrial process. SA is a typical self-ordering regime in sulfuric acid [53]. TSA-SA is a combination of the previous two, so as it has the same conditions as SA but in TSA electrolyte. After the first anodization, the anodized samples were immersed in 0.6 M H₃PO₄ at room temperature with magnetic stirring during 20 hours in order to remove the alumina layer. Afterwards, the second anodization was performed in the same conditions as the first anodization, as shown in Table 1. The second anodization of SA and TSA-SA was applied during 60 minutes in order to obtain layers with similar thickness to TSA, 3 μm approximately. The voltage-time cycles applied for the second anodization are included in Fig. S1 of Supplementary Material. Finally, some layers were sealed in boiling deionized water during 60

minutes. Once prepared, the samples were kept in zip lock bags to minimize the exposure to air and moisture before the characterization.

2.2 Characterization of oxide layers

FEG-SEM images of the porous alumina layers were acquired in a FEI Nova NanoSEM 450 microscope in order to study the morphology. For cross-section and bottom-view characterization, the alumina layers were obtained by dissolving the metal from the non-anodized face in a CuCl_2/HCl solution prepared with 6.8 g $\text{CuCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 100 mL of 37 % HCl, and deionized water up to 200 mL. The free-standing membranes were then simply broken with tweezers. Selected bottom-view images were processed in DigitalMicrograph® (Gatan, Inc.) to obtain patterns through Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) analysis. The patterns obtained are used to analyze the order of the porous structure.

Potentiodynamic linear polarization tests (LP) and electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) measurements were conducted in three-electrode cells, making use of a PGSTAT302N potentiostat with frequency response analyzer (FRA) (Metrohm Autolab B.V.) controlled by the software NOVA 2.1. An Ag/AgCl double junction electrode from Metrohm (0.207 V/SHE, 25 °C) was employed as the reference electrode and the counter electrode was a net made of platinized titanium. The test solution was 0.59 M NaCl and the exposed surface of the working electrode was 1.5 cm². The samples were immersed during different periods of time in the electrolyte prior to the electrochemical measurements, 1 hour in the case of LP tests and up to 1000 hours for EIS. LP tests were carried out from -0.25 V up to 2 V vs corrosion potential at a rate of 0.17 mVs⁻¹. The corrosion current densities of the samples were calculated through the Stern-Geary equation [54], using ± 10 mV around the open circuit potential to calculate polarization resistance (R_p) and assuming Tafel slopes of both cathodic and anodic reactions to

be 120 mV. The interval of the EIS measurements was between 100 kHz and 0.01 Hz. The amplitude selected was 10 mV.

2.3 EIS equivalent electric circuits

Anodic aluminum oxide coatings response to EIS measurements has been broadly studied during decades. Fig. 2a) schematizes the general equivalent electric circuit (EEC) successfully applied in many studies [28, 36, 55, 56]. Beginning at high frequencies range (close to 100 kHz) we find the resistance of the electrolyte, R_{el} , that is usually low because conductive solutions are employed, as it is the case of 0.59 M NaCl. Moving to medium frequencies range (around 0.1 Hz-1 kHz) there are two parallel branches with one time constant each of them. The first one comprises the response of the pore wall: the resistance of the pore walls, R_w , and a constant phase element accounting for the capacitance of the pore walls, CPE_w . The second branch contains the time constant associated to the sealing of the pores, with a resistor and a constant phase element, R_{po} and CPE_{po} , respectively. Finally, at the low frequencies range (close to 0.01 Hz), there is a third time constant in series with the latter. This third time constant is associated to the barrier layer electrical activity, comprising its resistance, R_{bl} , and a constant phase element representing its capacitive behavior, CPE_{bl} . CPEs are employed instead of pure capacitors to account for heterogeneities in the structure and capacitive behavior of the corresponding components of the real system. CPE is defined as [56]:

$$CPE = 1/(j2\pi fC)^n \quad (1)$$

“n” is a frequency dispersion factor varying from 0 to 1. When $n = 1$, the CPE is equivalent to a pure capacitor; when $n = 0$ is equivalent to a pure resistor. The described general EEC is conceived for the most complex situation when the pores are sealed. Many times, it should be

simplified or adapted. R_w and CPE_w are usually very high and very low, respectively, making the EEC 2b) often more useful. Furthermore, when the pores are not sealed the electrolyte fills the pores and the circuit can be reduced to 2c), associated solely to the response of the electrolyte, R_{el} , and the barrier layer, R_{bl} and CPE_{bl} . In the present work, equivalent electric circuits 1b) and 1c) have showed the best fitting results for sealed and unsealed samples, respectively.

3. Results

3.1 Morphology of unsealed samples

Top- and cross-section SEM images of samples TSA, SA and TSA-SA are included in Fig. 3. The mouths of the pores are observed in top-view images, being evident that TSA membrane features higher pore density and smaller pore diameter than SA and TSA-SA membranes. It may be a surprise that there is no clear order in the pore distribution of any top-view images, but the explanation relies on the growth mechanism of alumina and what is happening during the first seconds of anodizing. It is known that the porous anodic alumina is formed in the Al/Al₂O₃ interface by means of inward migration of oxygen-bearing species from the electrolyte and outward migration of Al³⁺ ions from the metal [40]. Therefore, fresh alumina grows below that previously formed and, as a consequence, the alumina in the electrolyte/Al₂O₃ interface was formed during the first moments of anodization. In our experimental set-up, the electrical regime applied takes a few seconds to get stable in 25 V for samples SA and TSA-SA. Likewise, the electrical cycle of TSA samples implies a ramp from 0 V up to 14 V during the first 5 minutes, as indicated in Table 1. That is, the outer surfaces of the porous anodic layers were not formed in self-ordering conditions.

Regarding cross sections, all samples have straight and parallel channels, indicating a noticeable degree of order. However, TSA sample looks less planar than the others and shows pores at

many different planes and levels. This fracture behavior may be caused by a lower degree of ordering in the sample TSA. The order can be better analyzed in the bottom-view images in Fig. 4. Thus, it can be observed that samples SA and TSA-SA show domains of well-ordered arrays of nanopores, in which the pores are arranged in a close-packed hexagonal lattice with six neighbors. Meanwhile, these hexagonal arrays cannot be observed in the bottom-view of TSA. Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) of bottom-view SEM images are included in the insets of Fig. 4. For an ideal close-packed hexagonal arrangement of the nanopores, a FFT pattern would be formed by six spots on the edges of a hexagon. Furthermore, depending on the magnification of the image, various concentric hexagons with increased number of spots can be seen because there are pores at increasing distances. It is schematized in the panel labelled Hexagonal. The occurrence of defects or disorder in the structure will modify the pattern into rings or even disc-shaped forms in case of high disorder [57-59].

TSA-SA is the structure showing the higher degree of order among the three bottom-view images. There are various ordered domains with different sizes and orientations in the SEM image. Each domain produces one or various concentric hexagons in the FFT image. However, there are also defects in the structure and the FFT pattern is slightly diffused. On the contrary, the structure of TSA is disordered and only a disc pattern can be seen in its corresponding FFT image. Sample SA is in an intermediate situation. SA shows several ordered domains with different orientations, although with smaller areas than those observed in sample TSA-SA. In addition, SA also has disordered domains and defects. The contributions of all of them give rise to the observed FFT pattern formed by concentric and diffused rings.

Therefore, although all three samples exhibit some degree of order in the cross-section images, the degree of order can be better analyzed according to the bottom-view images, being in the order $TSA \ll SA < TSA-SA$.

In any case, the fact that TSA sample presents a certain order in the vertical growth of the pores

is an interesting finding. It indicates that a high purity aluminum alloy, devoid of intermetallic that hamper the growth of anodic layer [60], besides the electropolishing before anodizing favor the order even in the case of TSA conditions, which are far from the usual parameters of self-ordering anodizing in sulfuric acid [40,53].

The ideal morphology of ordered anodic alumina membrane is schematized in Fig. 5. The main structural parameters defining this configuration are interpore distance (D_{int}), pore diameter (D_{po}), pore wall thickness (t_w), barrier layer thickness (t_{bl}), pore density (ρ_{po}) and porosity or void fraction (P). These parameters can be measured from electron microscopy images or calculated by means of geometrical relationship between them, such as those in equations (1) to (3).

$$D_{int} = D_{po} + 2t_w \quad (1)$$

$$\rho_{po} = 2/(\sqrt{3} \times D_{int}^2) \quad (2)$$

$$P(\%) = (\pi/(2 \times \sqrt{3})) \times (D_{po}/D_{int}) \times 100 \quad (3)$$

Table 2 shows some parameters obtained from SEM images of samples SA, TSA and TSA-SA. Firstly, D_{po} can be measured in top-view images (D_{po} top-view). Average of 100 measurements gives 10 ± 2 , 13 ± 3 and 10 ± 2 nm for TSA, SA and TSA-SA, respectively. D_{po} distribution can be found in Supplementary Material Fig. S2. Other authors report similar pore diameter for anodic layers obtained in TSA electrolyte on other aluminum alloys, such as 8 nm [28] or 10-15 nm [55]. However, as it was previously mentioned, the outer part of the anodic layer was formed in the beginning of the anodization, when the self-ordering regime had not yet been reached. Consequently, the diameters in the opening of the pores are different from those in the rest of the layer.

Equation (1) was used to make a more correct estimation of D_{po} . D_{int} was measured in the bottom-view images and $2t_w$ in the cross-section images. The pore diameter calculated with

equation (1) turns out to be 23 ± 6 , 22 ± 9 , and 26 ± 9 nm. They are, as expected, larger than those observed in top-view (D_{po} top view) but still very similar to each other. It was decided to use equation (1) instead of directly measuring the D_{po} in cross-section images for two reasons. First, because such a measure would only be correct if the cross-section was produced by the exact center of the pore, a fact that cannot be assured. Second, even if the cross-section was performed through the very center of the pore, D_{po} is smaller than D_{int} and $2t_w$, and its measurement hence implies larger error.

Other two important parameter derived from D_{int} and D_{po} are ρ_{po} and P. As observed in Table 1, TSA has higher ρ_p and P than SA and TSA-SA, roughly, 3-fold pore density and 2-fold porosity.

As a general conclusion of the morphological analysis included in Table 2, it can be drawn that all three samples have pores with similar diameter (D_{po}) but more closely placed in sample TSA. Meanwhile, SA and TSA-SA are very similar to each other.

3.2 Morphology of sealed samples

Fig. 6 includes SEM images of sealed samples, comparable to those of not sealed samples from Fig. 3. On the surface of all sealed samples characteristics flake-like structures are observed blocking the mouth of the pores. These structures have been described by other authors [28, 55, 61], In the cross sections it seems that the interior of the pores acquires a grainy texture when compared to images of unsealed samples, which would be due to partial hydration. Fig. 7 displays a cross-section view of the outer part of a sample TSA-SA-sealed, in which three areas can be distinguished. Firstly, the flake-like structures at the top, with approximately 0.5 microns of thickness. Next, a second compact zone in which the porous structure is not observed, presumably because the porous are completely sealed. And thirdly, it is observed the internal channels of the pores with the grainy texture described in cross-sections of Fig. 6.

However, it must be recognized that the study of the flake-like structure in section has found to be difficult and very few times was it possible to find areas free of defects. It should be reminded that membranes have 3 microns of thickness and they may suffer enough mechanical stress to detach or break the flakes when they are fractured and placed in sample holders.

3.3. Potentiodynamic polarization tests

Representative LP curves of samples not sealed and sealed have been plotted in Fig. 8, while their corresponding current density of corrosion (J_{corr}) and polarization resistance (R_p) are shown in Table 3. All anodic branches have a vertical area characteristic of passivation phenomena, in this case, due to the existence of the alumina layer. High cathodic slopes of unsealed samples are indicative of oxygen diffusion process control, whereas in the sealed samples a low cathodic slope denotes a mixed control response. [61]. There is an offset of the curves obtained from sealed samples to lower current densities and more negative potentials compared to their unsealed counterparts, which results in a decrease in J_{corr} and an increase in R_p . The reduction in J_{corr} is justified because the pore-blocking precludes the transport of the charged species involved in the corrosion process between the solution bulk and the metal. From the electrochemical point of view and according to mixed potential theory, the simultaneous reduction of corrosion potential and J_{corr} could be ascribed to a reduction in the cathodic current. In effect, it can be assumed that the reduced values of current densities and corrosion potentials in sealed samples are associated with a reduced number and area of cathodic sites exposed to the electrolyte [19]. It should be mentioned that all values for J_{corr} and R_p obtained for 3-4 specimens of each type of sample are within the same order of magnitude. Except for samples TSA-SA-sealed, which exhibited high instability in all specimens tested. In any case, the corrosion parameters obtained in the three types of samples are of the same order of magnitude and do not neatly allow to establish differences between

them. Therefore, further analyses were performed by EIS.

3.4 EIS of samples unsealed

Fig. 9 presents the results of the Bode diagrams of modulus and impedance phase versus the frequency. Table 4 summarizes the best fitting values of the EEC schemed in Fig. 2c) for the samples in Fig. 9. The theoretical curves of the fitted circuit are very close to experimental curves in all samples, especially in the simplest case of not sealed samples. The estimated errors of the software for the elements of the fittings are lower than 15%, being CPE_{po} the element showing highest error. All three unsealed samples have very similar behavior. Starting at high frequencies in the modulus diagram, they start from a horizontal section with low modulus associated with the electrolyte resistance (R_{el}) and then plot a constant upward slope associated with the time constant ascribed to the barrier layer (R_{bl} and CPE_{bl}). The diagrams of their phases begin at the highest frequencies with descents associated with R_{el} , although without reaching 0° corresponding to an ideal resistance. They then rise and remain constant at 90° from approximately 1000 Hz to 0.01 Hz, attributed to the capacitive behavior of the barrier layer. In view of these data, it can be concluded that, in unsealed samples, the impedance modulus of SA and TSA-SA samples are higher than the impedance modulus of TSA sample in almost the entire frequency range studied. The three of them are only very similar at the highest frequencies, related to R_{el} . These curves have been fitted with circuit 1c). The fittings also indicate a slightly better behavior of the barrier layer of TSA-SA and SA, as it is observed in the estimation of R_{bl} in Table 4, of approximately $1 \cdot 10^{+8} \Omega$, $2 \cdot 10^{+8} \Omega$ and $4 \cdot 10^{+8} \Omega$ for TSA, SA, and TSA-SA samples, respectively.

There are two factors that could explain these differences. The first and most intuitive is the thickness of the barrier layer. While the second factor is a difference in its electrical properties. Curioni *et al* [31] argue that the addition of tartaric acid to sulfuric acid electrolytes does not

significantly alter the electrical properties of the anodic oxide. While others [55] do suggest this possibility to explain a higher R_{bl} of an SA sample with thinner barrier layer contrasted with a lower R_{bl} of a TSA sample with thicker barrier layer.

The thickness of the barrier layer (D) can be calculated using the expression that defines a capacitor, equation (4):

$$D = (e \cdot e_0 \cdot S) / C_{bl} \quad (4)$$

Where $e = 10$ is the alumina dielectric constant, $e_0 = 8.854 \cdot 10^{-14} \text{ F}\cdot\text{cm}^{-1}$ is the dielectric constant in vacuum and $S = 1.5 \text{ cm}^2$ is the surface area tested. Although the EEC offering the best results includes a constant phase element (CPE_{bl}) instead of a capacitor (C), the n values of CPE_{bl} are very close to 1, so we have considered that CPE_{bl} values can be entered into the equation to obtain estimates. Thus, according to the data in Table 4, the barrier layers of TSA, SA and TSA-SA samples would be 10, 31 and 29 nm thick. These values are similar to estimations made in cross-section SEM images (Supplementary material Fig. S3). Although this calculation also has errors coming from the fitting of the experimental data to the equivalent circuit, the thickness (D) and C_{bl} are inversely proportional in equation (4). Therefore, based on the values in Table 4, the barrier layers of SA and TSA-SA are thicker than the barrier layer in TSA. That is, the different thickness could explain the higher impedance of the barrier layer of SA and TSA-SA. In any case, regardless of the causes, the TSA-SA modulus in the Bode diagram is higher than the TSA modulus. This indicates that the ordered conditions facilitate the formation of a barrier layer with greater protective capacity, as both layers were formed in the same electrolyte.

3.5 EIS of samples sealed

All sealed samples display higher impedance modulus at medium frequencies than their

unsealed counterparts, which involve the appearance of a horizontal section in the modulus diagram and its corresponding drop of the phase at angles below 90° in the phase diagram. These data indicate the filling of pores, at least partially, as verified by SEM, and the inclusion in the equivalent circuit of the time constant R_{po}/CPE_{po} . Samples sealed have been fitted to EEC 1b).

When the impedance at the low frequencies range are compared, in the region associated to the barrier layer, the modulus of SA-sealed and TSA-SA-sealed samples are higher than the modulus of TSA-sealed (Fig. 9a). Likewise, SA-sealed and TSA-SA-sealed show higher and wider phase angle than TSA-sealed in the low frequency region (Fig. 9b). As a consequence, SA-sealed sample and TSA-SA-sealed sample have better corrosion resistance than TSA-sealed sample. However, these results are not completely clear in the fitted values of R_{bl} , which are very similar. The reason may be that R_{bl} is very high, out of the frequency range tested and its fitting is not good enough.

The curves in Fig. 9 reveal that the TSA-sealed sample is the best sealed one, since its modulus in the medium frequencies range is higher than the modulus of the other samples. The fittings provide $R_{po} = 60620 \Omega$ for TSA-sealed, clearly higher than 6384Ω and 26090Ω for SA-sealed and TSA-SA-sealed, respectively. It can be found three hypotheses in the literature to explain the different sealing behavior of porous anodic alumina obtained in tartaric-sulfuric and sulfuric electrolytes. Firstly, various authors have shown that anodic layers produced on 2000 series aluminum alloys in TSA baths and sealed in boiling water have higher corrosion resistances than similar samples prepared in sulfuric acid baths [34, 55]. It has been suggested that the reason relies on the residual tartaric acid retained inside the pores after anodizing, which chelates Cu(II) ions present in the anodic film coming from the metal, promoting the homogeneity of the sealed layer [34]. In our case, we are working with a high purity aluminum alloy. Consequently, the formation of an important number of Cu(II)-chelates is difficult to conceive. Boisier *et al* [55] have proposed as a second hypothesis that the chemical environment

within the pores, for example pH, are more favorable to the precipitation of aluminum hydroxide in the presence of both tartaric salts and sulfates and less favorable when there are only sulfates. This suggestion could be plausible in our case because R_{po} of TSA-sealed is higher than R_{po} of SA-sealed. However, TSA-sealed also has higher R_{po} than TSA-SA-sealed. Therefore, the presence of tartrate anions is, at least, not the only explanation. Thirdly, it is also argued in [55] that the quality of the sealing depends on the volume of pores to be sealed (P), being more efficient in layer exhibiting less porosity. The results shown here in Table 2 lead to think in the opposite scenario, since TSA shows the highest calculated porosity among the three samples: $52 \pm 15\%$. While SA and TSA-SA have $28 \pm 12\%$ and $32 \pm 11\%$.

In view of this situation, we propose the degree of order of the porous structure as another variable justifying the differences observed in sealing efficiency. Accordingly, without ruling out that the other hypotheses may operate preferably in other circumstances (formation of Cu(II)-chelates, precipitation of aluminum hydroxide assisted by the presence of tartaric salts, and porosity), we argue that the degree of order appears to prevail in the samples here studied in such a way that samples showing less order (TSA) are more effectively sealed. The explanation could lie in the existence of branches, ripples and narrowings inside the pores, places that are easier to plug than straight and diaphanous channels. As an example of these heterogeneities, cross-section SEM images in Fig. 10 show some areas found in TSA samples where the pores did not grow parallel.

3.6 EIS of immersion tests

Corrosion tests were carried out by immersing samples TSA, SA, TSA-sealed and SA-sealed in aqueous 0.59 M NaCl at room temperature and monitoring their impedance at certain periods of time during 1000 hours. The results at the beginning of the experiment and after 500 hours and 1000 hours are included in Fig. 11a) for TSA and SA and in Fig. 11b) for samples TSA-sealed and SA-sealed. While Table 5 shows their corresponding fitted values of the elements in

the equivalent circuits. The estimated errors of the software for the elements of the fittings are lower than 15%, being CPE_{po} the element showing highest error. The data after 20 hours of immersion are the same previously presented in Fig. 9, employed again in Fig. 11 in order to discuss properly the evolution of the samples. Regarding the samples not sealed in Fig. 11a), it can be recalled that the modulus of sample SA starts being higher than the modulus of TSA over the whole frequency range. When the experiment progresses both samples increase their impedance in the area of high and medium frequencies, i.e. pores are sealed and the time constant R_{po}/CPE_{po} appears. The values of R_{po} increase with the time in both samples. This phenomenon in aqueous solution and even atmospheric exposure is known as self-sealing of the porous anodic layers. The alumina is hydrated in a similar way to the sealing process in boiling water, but with much slower rate [61, 62]. Similar to the results obtained for SA-sealed and TSA-sealed in Fig. 9, TSA is better self-sealed during the immersion test than SA and its modulus in the medium frequencies range increases faster, surpassing the modulus of SA after 1000 hours. The fitting to EEC in Fig. 2c) translates the experimental curves into the figures of Table 5, giving $R_{po(500h)} = 4915 \Omega$ and $R_{po(1000h)} = 18020 \Omega$ for TSA, and $R_{po(500h)} = 1573 \Omega$ and $R_{po(1000h)} = 5000 \Omega$ for SA. These figures provide an estimation of the different self-sealing ability of samples SA and TSA. Hence, SA requires 1000 hours of immersion to reach similar R_{po} than TSA after only 500 hours. Likewise, at the end of the experiment, R_{po} of TSA is almost four-fold R_{po} of SA.

Regarding n_{po} , this exponent is associated to the homogeneity of the sealing, being close to 1 when the sealing is very homogenous. Except the value 0.21 for SA 500h, which is lower than expected, n_{po} of SA 1000h, TSA 500h and TSA 1000h are near to 0.5. According to [36], it is reasonable that these values for n_{po} results from a vertical distribution of time constants. The pores should be only partially sealed, the composition of the precipitated products should not be homogeneous, and there are different geometric features so as the current would experience different values of dielectric constants through the pores down its bottom. On the contrary,

samples sealed in boiling water have $n_{po} \simeq 0.8$, which indicates their pores are more homogeneously sealed.

On the other side, as already discussed in section 3.4, SA-sealed 20h has higher modulus than TSA-sealed 20h in the high frequencies range associated to the barrier layer. Conversely, TSA-sealed 20h has higher impedance than SA-sealed 20h at medium and low frequencies because the pores of the former are better sealed. While the experiment is proceeding, the impedance at high frequencies remain unchanged but it increased at medium frequencies, similarly to samples not sealed, giving rise to an increase in R_{po} . In other words, sealed samples also undergo a self-sealing process. Therefore, the sealing treatment in boiling water during 60 minutes does not completely block the pores and the water infiltrate downwards the channels during the immersion test in such a way that the alumina is further hydrated, enhancing the resistance of the anodic layer. Analyzing in deeper detail the Table 5, it is observed that R_{po} of SA-sealed never reach similar values than those shown by TSA-sealed. Even R_{po} of TSA-sealed 20h (60620 Ω) is higher than R_{po} of SA-sealed 1000 h (34374 Ω). It is also found that TSA-sealed 500 h and TSA-sealed 1000 h have similar R_{po} . It could be due to the existence of a maximum resistance achievable by this system in the tested conditions. Alternatively, it may be due to the attack of the chloride ions to the alumina, which avoid a further increase in R_{po} .

4. Conclusions

The following conclusions can be drawn from the comparisons made between TSA, SA and TSA-SA samples:

- According to cross-section and bottom-view SEM images combined with FFT analysis, SA and TSA-SA have higher degree of order than TSA.
- Potentiodynamic polarization experiments do not allow to analyze how the order in the porous

AAO influences the corrosion behavior.

- SA and TSA-SA have higher impedance than TSA. The reason here suggested is that the self-ordering conditions promote thicker barrier layer in samples SA and TSA-SA.

- TSA samples are better sealed than SA and TSA-SA, both during a final treatment in boiling water and during self-sealing in 0.59 M NaCl at room temperature. It is proposed that samples showing lower degree of order (TSA) are sealed more efficiently due to the existence of disordered features such as branches, ripples and narrowings inside the pores.

As a whole, the results discussed herein point out that self-ordering anodizing is a suitable tool to improve the corrosion resistance of anodic aluminum oxide films obtained in TSA electrolyte. Notwithstanding, these preliminary results require further studies in order to assess the viability of the approach in an industrial scenario.

References

1. P.G. Sheasby, R. Pinner. The surface treatment and finishing of aluminum and its alloys. Sixth ed., Finishing Publications Ltd. UK. 2001.
2. J. Lawrence, D. L. O. Korb, Metals Handbook. Ninth ed., Volume 13, Corrosion. ASM International: 1987.
3. J. Wang, H. Fan, H. Zhang, Q. Chen, Y. Liu, W. Ma, Anodizing process of titanium and formation mechanism of anodic TiO₂ nanotubes, Prog. Chem. 28 (2016) 284-295.
4. A. Zimmer, D. Veys-Renaux, L. Broch, N. Stein, E. Rocca, Oxide growth mechanism on Mg AZ91 Alloy by anodizing: Combination of electrochemical and ellipsometric in-situ measurements, J. Electrochem. Soc. 164 (2017) C1059-C1066
5. K. Mika, R.P. Socha, P. Nyga, E. Wiercigroch, K. Małek, M. Jarosz, T. Uchacz, G.D. Sulka, L. Zaraska, Electrochemical synthesis and characterization of dark nanoporous zinc oxide films, Electrochim. Acta 305, (2019) 349-359.
6. H. Habazaki, T. Ogasawara, H. Konno, K. Shimizu, K. Asami, K. Saito, S. Nagata, P. Skeldon, G.E. Thompson, Growth of anodic oxide films on oxygen-containing niobium, Electrochim. Acta 50 (2005) 5334-5339.
7. M. Altomare, G. Cha, P. Schmuki, Anodic nanoporous niobium oxide layers grown in pure molten ortho-phosphoric acid, Electrochim. Acta 344 (2020) 136158.
8. T. Vignoli Machado, P. Atz Dick, G.H. Knörnschild, L.F.P. Dick, The effect of different carboxylic acids on the sulfuric acid anodizing of AA2024, Surf. Coat. Tech. 383 (2020) 125283.
9. M. Curioni, T. Gionfini, A. Vincenzo, P. Skeldon, G.E. Thompson, Optimization of anodizing cycles for enhanced performance, Surf. Interface Anal. 45 (2013) 1485-1489.
10. S. Stojadinovic, M. Tadic, I. Belca, B. Kasalica, L. Zekovic, The galvanoluminescence spectra of barrier oxide films on aluminum formed in organic electrolytes, Electrochim. Acta 52 (2007) 7166-7170.
11. J. Lu, G. Wei, Y. Yu, C. Guo, L. Jiang, Aluminum alloy AA2024 anodized from the mixed acid system with enhanced mechanical properties, Surf. Interfaces 13 (2018) 46-50.
12. M. Bethencourt, F.J. Botana, J.J. Calvino, M. Marcos, M.A. Rodríguez-Chacón, Lanthanide compounds as environmentally-friendly corrosion inhibitors of aluminum alloys: A review. 1998, Corros. Sci. 40 (1998) 1803-1819.
13. R.L. Twite, G.P. Bierwagen, Review of alternatives to chromate for corrosion protection of aluminum aerospace alloys, Prog. Org. Coat. 33 (1998) 91-100.
14. M. Becker, Chromate-free chemical conversion coatings for aluminum alloys. Corros. Rev. 37 (2019) 321-342.

15. M.F. Montemor, Functional and smart coatings for corrosion protection: A review of recent advances, *Surf. Coat. Tech.* 258 (2014) 17–37.
16. G.E. Thompson, L. Zhang, C.J.E. Smith, P. Skeldon, Boric/Sulfuric acid anodizing of aluminum alloys 2024 and 7075: film growth and corrosion resistance, *Corrosion* 55 (1999) 1052-1061.
17. S. Yu, L. Wan, C. Wu, T. Feng, Y. Cheng, Z. Bu, S. Zhu, Studies on the corrosion performance of an effective and novel sealing anodic oxide coating, *J. Alloy Compd.* 817 (2020) 153257.
18. Boeing Co., US. Patent 4,894,127 and 4,504,325.
19. M. García-Rubio, P. Ocón, A. Climent-Font, R.W. Smith, M. Curioni, G.E. Thompson, P. Skeldon, A. Lavia, I. García, Influence of molybdate species on the tartaric acid/sulfuric acid anodic films grown on AA2024 T3 aerospace alloy, *Corros. Sci.* 51 (2009) 2034-2042.
20. R. Wang, L. Wang, C. He, M. Lu, L. Sun, Studies on the sealing processes of corrosion resistant coatings formed on 2024 aluminium alloy with tartaric-sulfuric anodizing, *Surf. Coat. Tech.* 360 (2019) 369–375.
21. Y. Ma, X. Zhou, G.E. Thompson, M. Curioni, T. Hashimoto, P. Skeldon, P. Thomson, M. Fowles, Anodic film formation on AA 2099-T8 aluminum alloy in tartaric-sulfuric acid, *J. Electrochem. Soc.* 158 (2011) C17-C22.
22. US Patent 2002/0157961 A1. Anodizing process, with low environmental impact, for a workpiece of aluminum or aluminum alloys.
23. K.J. Kallenborn, J.R. Emmons, Thin film sulfuric acid anodizing as a replacement for chromic acid anodizing, *Aerospace Environmental Technology Conference*, Marshall Space Flight Center, 1995, pp. 267–276.
24. Z. Dinga, B.A. Smith, R. R. Hebert, W. Zhang, M.R. Jaworowski, Morphology perspective on chromic acid anodizing replacement by thin film sulfuric acid anodizing, *Surf. Coat. Tech.* 350 (2018) 31–39.
25. S. Fatimah, H.W. Yang, M-P. Kamil, Y.G. Ko, Control of surface plasma discharge considering the crystalline size of Al substrate, *Appl. Surf. Sci.* 477 (2019) 60-70.
26. V. Raj, M. Mubarak Ali, Formation of ceramic alumina nanocomposite coatings on aluminum for enhanced corrosion resistance, *J. Mater. Process. Tech.* 209 (2009) 5341-5352.
27. B. Kuznetsov, M. Serdechnov, J. Tedim, M. Starykevich, S. Kallip, M. P. Oliveira, T. Hack, S. Nixon, M. G. S. Ferreira, M. L. Zheludkevich, Sealing of tartaric sulfuric (TSA) anodized AA2024 with nanostructured LDH layers, *RSC Adv.* 6 (2016) 13942-13952.
28. V.R. Capelossi, M. Poelman, I. Recloux, R.P.B. Hernandez, H.G. De Melo, M.G. Olivier, Corrosion protection of clad 2024 aluminum alloy anodized in tartaric-sulfuric acid bath and protected with hybrid sol–gel coating, *Electrochim. Acta* 124 (2014) 69–79.

29. L. Zhang, G.E. Thompson, M. Curioni, P. Skeldon, Anodizing of Aluminum in Sulfuric Acid/Boric Acid Mixed Electrolyte, *J. Electrochem. Soc.* 160 (2013) C179-C184.
30. M. Whelan, K. Barton, J. Cassidy, J. Colreavy, B. Duffy, Corrosion inhibitors for anodised aluminum, *Surf. Coat. Tech.* 227 (2013) 75–83.
31. M. Curioni, P. Skeldon, E. Koroleva, G.E. Thompson, J. Ferguson, Role of Tartaric Acid on the Anodizing and Corrosion Behavior of AA 2024 T3 Aluminum Alloy, *J. Electrochem. Soc.* 156 (2009) C147-C153.
32. N. Du, S.-X. Wang, Q. Zhao, Z.-S. Shao, Effects of boric acid on microstructure and corrosion resistance of boric/sulfuric acid anodic film on 7050 aluminum alloy, *Trans. Nonferrous Met. Soc. China* 22 (2012) 1655-1660.
33. M. Norek, B. Budner, Effect of Various Electrolyte Modifiers on Anodic Alumina (AAO) Growth and Morphology, *Curr. Nanosci.* 15 (2019) 76-83.
34. M.A. Arenas, A. Conde, J.J. De Damborenea, Effect of acid traces on hydrothermal sealing of anodizing layers on 2024 aluminum alloy, *Electrochim. Acta* 55 (2010) 8704–8708.
35. M. Terada, F.M. Queiroz, D.B.S. Aguiar, V.H. Ayusso, H. Costenaro, M.-G. Olivier, H.G. de Melo, I. Costa, Corrosion resistance of tartaric-sulfuric acid anodized AA2024-T3 sealed with Ce and protected with hybrid sol–gel coating, *Surf. Coat. Tech.* 372 (2019) 422–426.
36. O.M. Prada Ramirez, F.M. Queiroz, M. Terada, U. Donatus, I. Costa, M.-G. Olivier, H.G. de Melo, EIS investigation of a Ce-based posttreatment step on the corrosion behaviour of Alclad AA2024 anodized in TSA, *Surf. Interface Anal.* 51 (2019) 1260–1275.
37. A. Renaud, M. Poorteman, J. Escobar, L. Dumas, Y. Paint, L. Bonnaud, P. Dubois, M.-G. Olivier, A new corrosion protection approach for aeronautical applications combining a Phenol-paraPhenyleneDiAmine benzoxazine resin applied on sulfo-tartaric anodized aluminum, *Prog. Org. Coat.* 112 (2017) 278–287.
38. A. Carangelo, M. Curioni, A. Acquesta, T. Monetta, F. Bellucci, Application of EIS to in situ characterization of hydrothermal sealing of anodized aluminum alloys: comparison between hexavalent chromium-based sealing, hot water sealing and cerium-based sealing, *J. Electrochem. Soc.* 163 (2016) C619-C626.
39. H. Masuda, K. Fukuda, Ordered metal nanohole arrays made by a two-step replication of honeycomb structures of anodic alumina, *Science* 268 (1995) 1466-1468.
40. W. Lee, S.-J. Park, Porous Anodic Aluminum Oxide: Anodization and Templated Synthesis of Functional Nanostructures, *Chem. Rev.* 114 (2014) 7487–7556.
41. S. Ateş, E. Baran, B. Yazıcı, The nanoporous anodic alumina oxide formed by two-step anodization, *Thin Solid Films* 648 (2018) 94-102.
42. UNE-EN 4704:2012 Tartaric-Sulphuric-Acid anodizing of aluminium and aluminium wrought alloys for corrosion protection and paint pre-treatment (TSA).

43. H. Sun, D. Sun, X. Shi, B. Li, D. Yue, R. Xiao, P. Ren, J. Zhang, PVA/SO₄²⁻-AAO difunctional catalytic-pervaporation membranes: Preparation and characterization, *Sep. Purif. Technol.* 241 (2020) 116739.
44. L.I. Lixia, Y. Liang, X. Zong, Y. Liu, Self-assembly plasmonic metamaterials based on templated annealing for advanced biosensing, *Opt. Express.* 28 (2020) 695-704.
45. X. Che, J. Boldrey, X. Zhong, S. Unnikandam-Veetil, I. Schneider, D. Jiles, L. Que, On-Chip studies of magnetic stimulation effect on single neural cell viability and proliferation on glass and nanoporous surfaces, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces.* 10 (2018) 28269-28278.
46. S. Cheng, S. Zhan, X. Wu, G. Nie, S. Wu, J. Hu, J. Li, S. Hu, Y. Zhang, Y. Liu, Insulating plasmonic photothermal heat of Ag nanoparticles by a thin carbon shell, *J. Alloy Compd.* 791 (2019) 380-384.
47. N. Van Toan, M.M.I.M. Hasnan, D. Udagawa, N. Inomata, M. Toda, S.M. Said, M.F.M. Sabri, T. Ono, Thermoelectric power battery using Al₂O₃ nanochannels of 10 nm diameter for energy harvesting of low-grade waste heat, *Energ. Convers. Manage.* 199 (2019) 111979.
48. A.M. Md Jani, D. Losic, N.H. Voelcker, Nanoporous anodic aluminum oxide: Advances in surface engineering and emerging applications, *Prog. Mater. Sci.* 58 (2013) 636-704.
49. Q. Wei, Y. Fu, G. Zhang, D. Yang, G. Meng, S. Sun, Rational design of novel nanostructured arrays based on porous AAO templates for electrochemical energy storage and conversion, *Nano Energy* 55 (2019) 234-259.
50. L. Bouchama, N. Azzouz, N. Boukmouche, J.P. Chopart, A.L. Daltin, Y. Bouznit, Enhancing aluminum corrosion resistance by two-step anodizing process, *Surf. Coat. Tech.* 235 (2013) 676-684.
51. S.J. Lee, S.J. Kim, Improvement of corrosion properties of Al-4.08Mg alloy in seawater by two step anodizing in electrolyte with varied concentration, *Acta Phys. Pol. A* 129 (2016) 742-746
52. M. Mehdizade, M. Soltanieh, A.R. Eivani, Investigation of anodizing time and pulse voltage modes on the corrosion behaviour of nanostructures anodic layer in commercial pure aluminum, *Surf. Coat. Tech.* 358 (2019) 741-752.
53. L. González-Rovira, M. López-Haro, A.B. Hungría, K. El Amrani, J.M. Sánchez-Amaya, J.J. Calvino, F.J. Botana, Direct sub-nanometer scale electron microscopy analysis of anion incorporation to self-ordered anodic alumina layers, *Corros. Sci.* 52 (2010) 3763-3773.
54. M. Stern, A.L. Geary, Electrochemical polarization: I. A theoretical analysis of the shape of polarization curves, *J. Electrochem. Soc.* 104 (1957) 56-63.
55. G. Boisier, N. Pébère, C. Druez, M. Villatte, S. Suel, FESEM and EIS Study of Sealed AA2024 T3 Anodized in sulfuric acid electrolytes: influence of tartaric acid, *J. Electrochem. Soc.* 155 (2008) C521-C529.

56. X.-H. Zhao, Y. Zuo, J.-M. Zhao, J.-P. Xiong, Y.-M. Tang, A study on the self-sealing process of anodic films on aluminum by EIS, *Surf. Coat. Tech.* 200 (2006) 6846-6853.
57. Y. Zeng, Z. Liu, W. Wu, F. Xu, J. Shi, Combining scanning electron microscopy and fast Fourier transform for characterizing mesopore and defect structures in mesoporous materials, *Micropor. Mesopor. Mat.* 220 (2016) 163-167]
58. L. Zaraska, W.J. Stępniewski, E. Ciepela, G.D. Sulka, The effect of anodizing temperature on structural features and hexagonal arrangement of nanopores in alumina synthesized by two-step anodizing in oxalic acid, *Thin Solid Films* 534 (2013) 155–161.
59. W.J. Stępniewski, A. Nowak-Stępniewska, M. Michalska-Domańska, M. Norek, T. Czujko, Z. Bojar, Fabrication and geometric characterization of highly-ordered hexagonally arranged arrays of nanoporous anodic alumina. *Pol. J. Chem. Tech.* 16, (2014) 63-69.
60. D. Veys-Renaux, N. Chahboun, E. Rocca, Anodizing of multiphase aluminum alloys in sulfuric acid: in-situ electrochemical behaviour and oxide properties, *Electrochim. Acta* 211 (2016) 1056–1065.
61. M. García-Rubio, M.P. de Lara, P. Ocón, S. Diekhoff, M. Beneke, A. Lavía, I. García, Effect of posttreatment on the corrosion behaviour of tartaric–sulfuric anodic films, *Electrochim. Acta* 54 (2009) 4789–4800.
62. M.J. Bartolomé, J.F. del Río, E. Escudero, S. Feliu Jr., V. López, E. Otero, J.A. González. Behaviour of different bare and anodised aluminum alloys in the atmosphere. *Surf. Coat. Tech.* 202 (2008) 2783–2793.

Acknowledgements

L.G.R. acknowledges support from the Programme for Attracting Talent of UCA

Funding:

This work was supported by Centro para el Desarrollo Tecnológico Industrial (CDTI) and Corporación tecnológica de Andalucía (CTA)

Tables

Table 1.- Anodizing conditions.

Sample	Alloy	Electrolyte	Temperature (°)	Voltage (V)	Time 1st anod.	Time 2nd anod.
TSA	Al 99.999%	0.41 M H ₂ SO ₄ (98%) 0.53 M C ₄ H ₆ O ₆	37	14*	20 min	-
SA	Al 99.999%	0.3 M H ₂ SO ₄ (98%)	5-7	25	20 h	60 min
TSA-SA	Al 99.999%	0.41 M H ₂ SO ₄ (98%) 0.53 M C ₄ H ₆ O ₆	5-7	25	20 h	60 min

* Initial voltage ramp from the open circuit potential (OCP) to 14 V at 2.8 V/min.

Table 2.- Structural parameters of samples TSA, SA and TSA-SA. (\pm Standard deviation)

Sample	D_{po} Top-view (nm)	D_{int} (nm)	2t_w (nm)	D_{po ec.} (1) (nm)	ρ_{po} (cm⁻²)	P(%)
TSA	10 \pm 2	40 \pm 5	17 \pm 4	23 \pm 6	7.22·10 ¹⁰ \pm 1.80·10 ¹⁰	52 \pm 15
SA	13 \pm 3	71 \pm 5	49 \pm 7	22 \pm 9	2.29·10 ¹⁰ \pm 3.23·10 ⁹	28 \pm 12
TSA-SA	10 \pm 2	73 \pm 4	47 \pm 8	26 \pm 9	2.17·10 ¹⁰ \pm 2.37·10 ⁹	32 \pm 11

Table 3.- Electrochemical parameters obtained from Fig. 8.

Sample	J_{corr} (Acm⁻²)	R_p (Ωcm²)
TSA	$7.04 \cdot 10^{-7}$	$3.73 \cdot 10^{+4}$
TSA_sealed	$9.07 \cdot 10^{-11}$	$2.87 \cdot 10^{+8}$
SA	$7.40 \cdot 10^{-7}$	$3.52 \cdot 10^{+4}$
SA_sealed	$9.85 \cdot 10^{-11}$	$2.65 \cdot 10^{+8}$
TSA-SA	$2.63 \cdot 10^{-7}$	$1.20 \cdot 10^{+5}$
TSA-SA_sealed	-	-

Table 4.- Fitted parameter values of EIS curves in Fig. 9 to EEC of Fig. 2b (sealed) and Fig. 2c (unsealed).

Sample	R_{bl} (Ω)	CPE_{bl} ($F S^{(n-1)} cm^{-2}$)	n_{bl}	R_{po} (Ω)	CPE_{po} ($F S^{(n-1)} cm^{-2}$)	n_{po}
TSA	$1.15 \cdot 10^8$ ($\pm 0.3 \cdot 10^8$)	$1.31 \cdot 10^{-6}$ ($\pm 0.1 \cdot 10^{-6}$)	0.97 (± 0.01)	-	-	-
TSA_sealed	$1.15 \cdot 10^8$ ($\pm 0.4 \cdot 10^8$)	$2.55 \cdot 10^{-6}$ ($\pm 0.6 \cdot 10^{-6}$)	0.94 (± 0.11)	60620 (± 29042)	$3.08 \cdot 10^{-8}$ ($\pm 0.4 \cdot 10^{-8}$)	0.85 (± 0.1)
SA	$2.14 \cdot 10^8$ ($\pm 0.2 \cdot 10^8$)	$4.29 \cdot 10^{-7}$ ($\pm 0.4 \cdot 10^{-7}$)	0.99 (± 0.01)	-	-	-
SA_sealed	$2.14 \cdot 10^8$ ($\pm 0.2 \cdot 10^8$)	$6.21 \cdot 10^{-7}$ ($\pm 0.2 \cdot 10^{-7}$)	0.91 (± 0.02)	6384 (± 1160)	$8.68 \cdot 10^{-8}$ ($\pm 2.0 \cdot 10^{-8}$)	0.79 (± 0.2)
TSA-SA	$4.06 \cdot 10^8$ ($\pm 0.4 \cdot 10^8$)	$4.60 \cdot 10^{-7}$ ($\pm 0.9 \cdot 10^{-7}$)	0.98 (± 0.01)	-	-	-
TSA- SA_sealed	$1.15 \cdot 10^8$ ($\pm 0.3 \cdot 10^8$)	$5.30 \cdot 10^{-7}$ ($\pm 0.6 \cdot 10^{-7}$)	0.96 (± 0.04)	26090 (± 9515)	$1.41 \cdot 10^{-7}$ ($\pm 0.5 \cdot 10^{-7}$)	0.79 (± 0.4)

*In brackets, standard deviation from fitting of 3 samples

Table 5.- Fitted parameter values of EIS curves in Fig. 11 to EEC of Fig. 2b and Fig. 2c.

Sample	R_{bl} (Ω)	CPE_{bl} ($F S^{(n-1)} cm^{-2}$)	n_{bl}	R_{po} (Ω)	CPE_{po} ($F S^{(n-1)} cm^{-2}$)	n_{po}
SA 20h	$2.14 \cdot 10^8$	$4.29 \cdot 10^{-7}$	0.989	-	-	-
SA 500h	$2.46 \cdot 10^8$	$4.81 \cdot 10^{-7}$	0.965	1573	$6.36 \cdot 10^{-5}$	0.21
SA1000h	$2.49 \cdot 10^8$	$5.00 \cdot 10^{-7}$	0.960	5000	$6.13 \cdot 10^{-6}$	0.42
TSA 20h	$1.15 \cdot 10^8$	$1.31 \cdot 10^{-6}$	0.974	-	-	-
TSA 500h	$2.97 \cdot 10^8$	$1.93 \cdot 10^{-6}$	0.970	4915	$1.30 \cdot 10^{-5}$	0.43
TSA 1000h	$4.11 \cdot 10^8$	$1.43 \cdot 10^{-6}$	0.967	18020	$5.91 \cdot 10^{-6}$	0.41
SA_sealed 20h	$2.14 \cdot 10^8$	$6.21 \cdot 10^{-7}$	0.91	6384	$8.68 \cdot 10^{-8}$	0.79
SA_sealed 500h	$2.14 \cdot 10^8$	$6.31 \cdot 10^{-7}$	0.95	15989	$4.49 \cdot 10^{-8}$	0.82
SA_sealed 1000h	$2.14 \cdot 10^8$	$6.00 \cdot 10^{-7}$	0.95	34374	$3.34 \cdot 10^{-8}$	0.84
TSA_sealed 20h	$1.15 \cdot 10^8$	$2.55 \cdot 10^{-6}$	0.94	60620	$3.08 \cdot 10^{-8}$	0.85
TSA_sealed 500h	$1.15 \cdot 10^8$	$2.38 \cdot 10^{-6}$	0.91	$1.15 \cdot 10^5$	$4.39 \cdot 10^{-8}$	0.82
TSA_sealed 1000h	$1.15 \cdot 10^8$	$3.01 \cdot 10^{-6}$	0.76	$1.13 \cdot 10^5$	$3.73 \cdot 10^{-8}$	0.83

List of figure captions

Fig. 1.- Schematic representation of the two-step anodizing process.

Fig. 2.- a) General equivalent electric circuit used to model porous anodic alumina layers, b) simplified equivalent electric circuit used for sealed samples and, c) simplified equivalent electric circuit used for unsealed samples.

Fig. 3.- SEM images of the anodic layer of samples TSA, SA and TSA-SA. Top-view (first row) and cross-section (second row).

Fig. 4.- Bottom-view SEM images of the anodic layer of samples TSA, SA and TSA-SA. A scheme of a perfect close-packed hexagonal structure of hexagonal cells. FFT patterns of the SEM images and the scheme in the corresponding insets.

Fig. 5.- Schematic representation of characteristic parameters of the structure of ordered porous AAO. D_{int} : interpore distance; D_{po} : pore diameter; t_w : pore wall thickness; t_{bl} : barrier layer thickness.

Fig. 6.- SEM images of the anodic layer of samples TSA-sealed, SA-sealed and TSA-SA-sealed. Top-view (first row) and cross-section (second row).

Fig. 7.- Cross-section SEM image of the outer part of the anodic layer of a sample TSA-SA-sealed.

Fig. 8.- Potentiodynamic polarization curves after 1 hour of immersion in 0.59 M NaCl of samples TSA, SA, TSA-SA, TSA-sealed, SA-sealed and TSA-SA-sealed.

Fig. 9.- Bode diagrams of experimental and fitted data of a) modulus and b) phase for samples TSA, SA, TSA-SA, TSA-sealed, SA-sealed and TSA-SA-sealed after 20 hours of immersion

in 0.59 M NaCl. Unsealed samples were fitted to EEC in Fig. 2c. Sealed samples were fitted to EEC in Fig. 2b.

Fig. 10.- Cross-section SEM images of the anodic layer of samples TSA showing disordered areas where the pores are not parallel.

Fig. 11.- Bode diagrams of experimental and fitted data of modulus after 20, 500 and 1000 hours of immersion in 0.59 M NaCl, a) samples SA and TSA, fitted to EEC in Fig. 2b; b) samples SA-sealed and TSA-sealed, fitted to EEC in Fig. 2c.

Fig. 1

Fig. 2

Fig. 3

Fig. 4

Fig. 5

Fig. 6

Fig. 7

Fig. 8

Fig. 9

Fig. 10

Fig. 11

Supplementary Material

Supplementary Material. Fig. S1. Voltage-time cycles applied for the second anodization.

Supplementary Material. Fig. S2. Pore diameter distribution obtained from top-view SEM images.

Supplementary Material. Fig. S3. Estimation of barrier layer thickness in cross-section SEM images.